

CAREER PATH OF PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES

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Abstract: *This study aims to determine the career path of employed persons with disabilities. It deals with the transition of PWD after secondary education and presents the problem encountered by the PWD in their employment. Purposive sampling was utilized to obtain the participants in this qualitative research. Fifteen employed PWD research participants were identified and interviewed to determine their career path. Secondary research participants were also identified in the National Capital Region such as SPED Teachers and SPED Coordinators both in public and private schools, and parents with PWD children. The purpose was to confirm the transition program in school and the difficulties encountered by PWD. The study revealed that transitions for PWD were chosen according to the disability. Persons with physical disabilities due to poliomyelitis and visual impairment usually continue their studies up to the tertiary level. They are also competitive with the regular students starting from elementary level. They also hold higher position in the field of work they belong. On the other hand, persons with hearing impairment engage in vocational courses to get job training. In addition, students with Autism and Down's syndrome sometimes enroll in a non-graded school to enhance their skills. However, speech therapy is always accommodated to improve speech and communication. In addition, parents of these PWD do not allow them to travel alone. They should be assisted by having buddies with them all the time. Their parents consider their submissive attitudes as making them vulnerable to abuse. Implications and future directions are discussed.*

Keywords: Persons with disability, employment, transition

INTRODUCTION

Employment among persons with disabilities has been a relevant world issue especially in recent years. The World Health Organization reported that according to the International Labor Organization (ILO), claims for disability benefits are surging in industrialized countries reaching up to 600 per cent, Kraus (2015). Governments, companies, and unions are encouraged to search for ways to get disabled people back to work. In the case of unemployed persons with disabilities, two thirds of them would like to work but they could not find a job. Furthermore, in the United States where Special Education has been well established, a 2004 survey found that only 35 per cent of working-age persons with disabilities were in fact working, compared to the 78 per cent of those with disabilities. One third of the employees surveyed said that persons with disabilities could not effectively perform the required job tasks. The second most common

reason given for not hiring persons with disabilities was the fear of costly special facilities. In the Philippines, one of the major economic problems is mainly centered on employment. Based on a report in 2010, millions of Filipinos were either unemployed or underemployed, Gaynor (2015). Persons with disabilities (PWDs) are not exempted from experiencing the economic crisis today. Despite disabilities, many of them work based on their specialized studies in skills areas (Philippine Star, 2014, 2006, 2013). Mori et al. (2009) surveyed in their study that half of the PWDs in Metro Manila had income-generating jobs.

Likewise, poverty is very much linked to unemployment. One solution to poverty of a family involves the work-related activity of parents in order to sustain the needs of the entire family. Children are sent to school or trained to operate a business so that when they get to adult stage, they will be able to feed themselves and their families (Manuel, 2012).

The first goal of United Nation's reduces poverty and enhance work and employment prospects ESCA (2012) states that PWD experience significant labor market disadvantage, have less economic participation and hence are disproportionately poorer than persons without disabilities. To have a decent job, education, training and support will lift PWD and their families out of poverty and will contribute to the achievement of inclusive growth and sustainable development.

Persons with disability should be treated fairly in the society. In view of this, the Commissioner on Human Rights of the Philippines Maria Asuncion I. Mariano-Maravilla (2014) signed an advisory in relation to human-based approach in celebration of the 36th National Disability Prevention and Rehabilitation Week. The human rights-based approach to disability states that the commission seeks to ensure that the dignity, human rights, and the freedom of all persons, including persons with disabilities, are always respected, promoted, and protected in a rights-based approach since PWDs have the same human rights as others do and therefore, must be able to enjoy them on an equal basis with others.

A child with disability undergoes trainings from home to school. These trainings include home living, academic and social activities. Work and job opportunities are provided to a child after secondary education. A person with disability, when normalized, performs as what others without (Dizon, 2002; Salamanca, 1999). With the proper skills training, a person with disability possibly can work. To achieve successful employment performance among persons with disability, a transition should be provided for them. Families with a child with disability try their best to help him/her live a normal life.

Parents of students with disabilities look forward to a good future for their children. That's why during their basic education they see to it that their children are provided with an assessment, therapist, shadow teacher, and a special education teacher. After his child graduates from high school, a parent may ask himself about the future of his child. This is where a parent's decision comes in with regard to the choice of career for his/her child's adult life. A crisis among PWDs arises when situation comes when PWDs enter college because of parent's intention though they don't have the capacity to pursue such track. After graduation, one ends up to be idle in the house and not able to function well. These PWDs can enrol in TESDA instead and their skills and interests are the basis in the choice of their course so that they become more productive in career. Eventually, as they grow older, they also want to work just like

anyone around. The parents' responsibility is to find proper employment for them. At the same time parents also get older and leave their child alone when they die. Through trainings and employment, PWDs become stable in their jobs and independent as they live in the community (Aguilar, 2007; Cioco, 2007).

Employment comes after a person finishes education. One is determined and expected to be employed when he/she is at the right age. As early as 14 years old in developing countries, an individual can be admitted to employment based on the ILO Convention No. 138. (<http://www.ble.dole.gov.ph>). An individual is expected to have a career in order to sustain his/her livelihood. In pursuance of education after secondary, transition or the post-secondary education assists youth with special needs to achieve career destination (Halpen, 1985, 1993; Brolin, 1989; Evers, 2013). Beforehand, an assessment should be provided for proper guidance and implementation. Although youth with disabilities do less in mental or physical faculties, through transition services these employed youth become capable to themselves, with respect to others, and to the community (Monahan, 2003; Roessler, Hennessey, Hogan, Savickas, 2009).

The aim of the present study is to determine the career path of persons with disabilities towards employment. Specifically, the following research questions are addressed: (1) What are the transition services available to persons with disabilities (PWDs) towards employment in the following areas: (1.1) further schooling, (1.2) job training, and (1.3) employment? (2) How do families and schools participate in the planning and implementation of the career path of youth with disabilities? (3) What jobs are the persons with disabilities employed in and what is the nature of their jobs? (4) To which factors do parents attribute the employment of their children with disabilities? (5) How do youth with disabilities face the challenges to transition? (6) What transition program can be developed based on the results of the study?

METHODS

Descriptive research method with multiple cases studies through qualitative and quantitative approaches research were utilized in this study. The researcher analysed the data inductively. The researcher used a one-on-one interview to gather data. The researcher conducted case studies and analyzed the commonalities of each case's answers in relation to the problem. Fraenkel, Wallen and Hyun (2012); Arthur et al (2012). Purposive sampling was utilized to obtain the participants of this research. Nominations were

requested from the agencies and institutions. Fifteen employed persons with disabilities in the National Capital Region were involved in this study. Nine were males while six were females. The identified disabilities of participants were: physical disabilities due to poliomyelitis (4), orthopaedic disability (1), spinal cord injury, autism (1), visually impaired (2), hearing impaired (3) and down syndrome (2). The main criteria for the selection of the primary research participant were that he should be an employed PWD to determine the career path. In gathering the initial data, the researcher wrote a requesting permission letter to the institutions and centers that employ PWD. Through these institutions the researcher was provided enough participants for this study. The selected institutions that helped the researcher in interviewing the employed PWD were: a café that trains with autism and down syndrome as crew, a toothpaste and personal care product manufacturer employing persons with hearing impairments, a private agency that delivers education services for children and people with visual impairments, a rehabilitation and skills training center for persons with physical disabilities, a government agency that formulate policies and coordinate the activities of all public and private agencies, a pharmaceutical company that hires a regular employee with autism and a pioneering SPED school that offers apprenticeship for students with special needs.

Secondary research participants were also identified at the National Capital Region which includes employed PWD, SPED Teachers, SPED Coordinators, and parents with PWD children. The purpose was to confirm the transition program in school and the difficulty encountered by PWD. To conduct interview from public schools, the researcher requested permission through letters from the superintendents of the divisions in Manila and Quezon City.

In the conduct of FGD, the researcher was able to form three groups namely: a) PWD, b) Parents, and c) Teachers. Two groups were conducted for FGD PWD. One was held at the National Council for Disability Affairs (NCDA) Library and the other one at the government high school institution. The researcher wrote a letter to the Executive Director of NCDA asking permission to conduct FGD in their department. Four employees attended. One had hearing impairment, another one had orthopedic disability and two with physical disabilities due to poliomyelitis. At the government high school institution six attended. Five of them had hearing impairment and one with behavioral problem. Attendees were all alumni of this school.

For Parents FGD, the researcher consulted a university Special Education

department office and the university Technical Education and Skills Development Center (TESDC). The researcher got the records of the PWD high school graduates who took short courses such as culinary, baking, and automotive. The researcher also got the names of their parents and their telephone numbers. Out of 21, five parents responded and attended the FGD. The discussion was held at the university Special Education department office.

For Teachers FGD, the researcher wrote a letter to the superintendents of the Manila Division Office and Quezon City Division Office. After three days the letters were approved and right after the approval on the same day, the researcher proceeded to the Principal's Offices of two public high schools in Manila to submit the approved letter. Since the principals were not around, the researcher left the letters. Eleven teachers attended. Another day was set to see the Principals of two public high schools in Quezon City. The Principals were present and approved the requests immediately. After the approval of the Principal, the secretary of one public high school in Quezon City escorted the researcher to the other building to meet the SPED Coordinator. The SPED Coordinator set a schedule of FGD. Five teachers attended. At the other public high school in Quezon City, the officer in charge of the day endorsed the researcher to the SPED Coordinator to set the schedule for FGD. During FGD, two teachers attended. The FGDs of four schools were held in their respective schools due to the policy of the DepEd that there should be no disruption of classes. The FGD was held during the mid-shift of the morning and afternoon teachers. In one private and pioneering SPED in Quezon City, two teachers attended in FGD. Seven SPED Coordinators were interviewed from 7 different schools in Manila and Quezon City.

INSTRUMENTS

Interview Guide. Two interview guides were used: one for employed person with disability and another one for SPED Coordinator. One interview guide for parents was used as support for the interview for employed person with autism. The researcher improvised a cardboard chart which was cut according to items to be more comfortable in asking question during the interview. The questions asked in the interviews for PWD and for focus group discussion for PWD, parents, school administrator, and teachers were related to the problem of the study which was the basis of determining the career path of the persons with disabilities. After the construction of the interview guide, a trial was tested to at least one employed person with disability and one school administrator in one university who were not included in the study to check the content

validity and face validity. Since the questions were very simple there was no revision made but they suggested that if the respondent would have difficulty in answering, the researcher would translate it to Filipino. This was possible because the researcher was the only interviewer. One copy of each questionnaire for PWD, parent, and school administrator constructed by the researcher was used while conducting an interview with the participants. While the researcher asked questions, the answers were recorded through a video recorder. The researcher held three sets of questionnaire that each questionnaire's item was pasted in a cardboard and was used in a one-on-one interview with the respondent while the video camera on the tripod was set to play. The interview lasted for one hour. Then, the recorded interviews were transcribed by the researcher.

Interviews. Interview protocol was observed before the interview was administered. Before the conduct of interviews, the researcher set the schedule through telephone calls and personal visit to the workplace. Then, the researcher went back to the workplace to conduct the actual interview. The answers to the questions were recorded by the researcher using a video recorder. During the interview, the researcher used probing strategy to clarify any questions that were obscure. The researcher also asked the participant to expand the answers that were particularly important or revealing. For interview with hearing impairment participants, the researcher requested an interpreter to translate the question and answer through sign language. The completion of the interview took three months. The researcher accomplished one interview in a day due to distance and traffic problems on the road. Furthermore, the researcher established a comfortable rapport with participants so that the respondents answered as exhaustively as they could. Semi-structured interview protocol uses "probes" throughout the interview to draw out the participant. In the interviews, behaviors of the employed persons with disabilities were observed in their workplaces.

Focus group discussion. The researcher conducted three focus group discussions from among employed PWD, teachers in high school and parents with children with PWD. The topic focused on the career path of persons with disabilities. An FGD Protocol was prepared before the scheduled date and time. The protocol was divided into three phases: before, during, and after. These phases guided the researcher to conduct the FGD properly. There were five questions prepared which yielded the research's statement of the problem

DATA ANALYSIS

Qualitative data obtained from the participants' interviews, observations, and focus group discussions were analysed through coding to form a concept (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Codes were categorized and analysed thematically (Glaser and Strauss, 1985; Miles and Huberman, 1984). After an interview with PWD and FGD with parents, SPED teachers and SPED coordinators, the researcher transcribed the video recorded interviews manually. Their answers were arranged according to the statement of the problems in the study. The researcher identified the themes and created codes. Subcodes were also produced until they were finalized to combine related codes. The codes were tabulated according to the frequency of responses. The tabulated responses were ranked from highest to the lowest. Each table of ranked codes was interpreted.

RESULTS

Transition Services. Transitions of PWD were chosen according to their disabilities. Based on a transition framework three options one PWD can take: (1) further schooling, (2) job training, and (3) job employment (Dizon, 2012). Persons with physical disabilities due to poliomyelitis and visually impaired usually continue their studies up to tertiary level. They were also competitive with the regular students starting from elementary level. They also held higher position in the field of work for which they belonged. However, due to financial constraints, they can approach government assistance and scholarship grants. Ramps and elevators for wheelchair persons are better be provided in schools and workplaces for accessibility. Persons with hearing impairment engaged in vocational courses to get job training after taking the 2-year course, to be qualified for work. During their secondary level, they connected to each other and found work together. They were influential to one another aside from getting assistance from their teachers. These students need more interpreters in classrooms and in workplaces. In addition, students with autism and down syndrome sometimes enrolled in a non-graded school to enhance their skills. Speech therapy was always accommodated to improve speech and communication. However, parents of these PWD did not allow them to travel alone. They should be assisted by having buddies with them all the time. As parents confirmed about their being submissive and tended them to be abused, they usually made and created jobs for them. It could be from their own family business or from the disability organization to which they belonged. Through the organization, PWD extended their connection all over the world. Due to this disability, enrolling to a non-graded school could be combined with job training to develop communication and social skills. Their working

age sometimes, were not at par with their mental age. On the other hand, persons with orthopedic disability and hearing impairment got employed right after secondary. Their main reasons were economic, and they wanted to help their parents and their family. Moreover, parents were the first ones to be involved in the planning and implementation of PWD career path.

Families and School Participation: In school, the SPED teachers were the foremost to plan and suggest to parents what career should the PWD have. Teachers connected to other government and non-government agencies so that employment would be delivered to PWD. Most of the transition programs were based on the TLE and K-12 curriculum. Livelihood program provided by non-government was catered in the school for six months summer time. Teachers who handled students with hearing impairment served as interpreters in applying job due to scarcity of interpreters in business companies. Teachers also tied-up and linked with other school and university that provided scholarship particularly with hearing impairment. Teachers suggested to parents the course to be taken up by their children. In the beginning of the school year, as early as Grade-7, teachers oriented and developed their students' skills to prepare them in work. Teachers oriented the parents that their child should become independent and mature while in the school.

PWD Employment: PWD could do any jobs as long as they coordinated with their interest, abilities, capabilities, disability, and availability of opportunities. For persons with hearing impairment who engaged mostly in vocational courses, they worked as computer graphics, cook, baker, machine operator, packaging, teacher, bar tender, and utilities. They were honest in terms of responsibilities at work. They started their work on time and finished it on time. They were also focused during the whole period of their work. Persons with poliomyelitis, orthopedic disability, and were visually impaired worked as high as an executive officer, teacher, government officer-in-charge, and manager. Moreover, person with spinal cord injury could be a welder for customized wheel chairs. Furthermore, persons with autism and Down Syndrome worked based on their skills and talents like painting, baking, cooking, and crew at cafe. Parents usually stay behind their job because their parents were the ones who found and created jobs for them.

Parent's Attribution to PWD Employment: The parents' decision on the PWD rested on the assessment by a medical doctor, psychoeducational diagnostician, or clinical eye of the parent. The disability, interest, capability, job opportunity were considered in the

employment. Based on the disability, VI, HI, Physical and Orthopedic disability could proceed to tertiary level. They could study further after secondary. Those with Autism and Down Syndrome may develop skills and talents and proceed to work. With learning disability, PWD could do household chores. All of PWD were considered based on their talents and interest whether they were good at painting, dancing, speaking, leading, cooking, filing, and teaching.

Persons with physical disabilities mostly possessed a normal brain so they could meet the mental requirement of a regular with neurotypical individual. Other disability like autism could be classified as functional, high functional, low, moderate low. Those with Learning Disability and Down Syndrome had the lower ability. They were provided speech therapists and job coaches. Job opportunity for persons with autism is based on their skills.

PWD Facing the Challenges: To face the challenges of PWD to transition, PWD, parents, and teachers mentioned the difficulties they experienced in their secondary education and in their workplaces.

Financial Problem: PWD with physical disabilities due to poliomyelitis experienced lack of books and transportation allowance in her college studies and travelled along the highway using her wheelchair everyday for two years. Another with physical disability should engage in any kind of work to earn a living while studying. Families with low income resources limited PWD to be enrolled to school for further schooling. Even if they had the potential to perform as regular student, economic constraints hindered them from schooling. Provisions of services and accommodations are necessary to achieve one's goal. Parents with low generating income were instructed by teachers to approach NGOs, politicians, school alumni organization and government organization to avail themselves with scholarship grants.

Emotional Disturbance: Family and financial problems were experienced by person who could not walk because of spinal injury. He stayed in a dormitory to continue his living while riding in a wheelchair and worked to customize wheelchair.

Lack of Interpreter: Communication barriers happened between HI and other people around them. HI applicants who did not have interpreters in the company approached their teachers who knew sign language but sometimes could not help due to school obligations. However, licensed interpreters for hearing impairment were few and costly that HI could hardly afford. Moreover, companies did not provide for one applicant because it could mean paying another employee. Nonetheless even at

home, parents did not know how to use sign language for their child with hearing impairment. Because of lack of interpreter, an applicant would not be hired for work due to communication barrier. HI students were observed by their teachers to be low in comprehension due to their impairment. In addition, Lack of Communication is evident to those with Down Syndrome who were non-verbal and had very limited comprehension. They could be less understood by those who are non-PWD.

Security: Persons with Autism and with Down Syndrome could not be allowed to travel alone. Parents were always on their side wherever they went. Persons with Autism whether male or female had the tendency to be abused the reason why parents tend to be always on guard.

Employment: Persons with hearing impairment with different employment such as cook, bar tender, baker, graphic artist, product packager, and food delivery crew experienced difficulty in their work. They found out that it was harder to prepare food stuffs before cooking, produce and create stacks for cakes. They were under pressure in preparation for events, lacked focus and had difficulty in writing delivery items. Meanwhile, persons with physical disabilities due to poliomyelitis experienced bullying, inaccessibility in her workplaces and transportation. For parents, job opportunity for persons with Autism had no assurance of getting a job as non-PWD experienced underemployment and unemployment.

Rejection: Family, teacher, and community rejection was experienced by PWD. Until now, other parents are still on the denial of having a child with disability. For many years, the child had been enrolled in regular class to realize later on that he/she is already an adult. She was enrolled in high school due to age requirement but the mental ability and skills like communication, comprehension, motor, and social were not developed well which should start at their early years. Other parents enrolled their child to school for the purpose of avoiding responsibilities. They enrolled at Grades 7 to 10 with no appearance and collaboration with the teachers in school. On the other hand, the community rejected in a way that PWD were not accepted in the companies they applied for work especially for HI because of no available interpreter and lack of competency. Teachers from the regular classes rejected students with disabilities by verbally telling the SPED teachers to let their PWD students stay in the resource room. There was no collaboration applied between the SPED teachers and the regular teacher. Regular teachers showed discontentment and were unloving to PWD. In addition, limited

Companies accept PWD workers. The implementation of the Senate bill to have at least 5% disabled in companies passed in the senate bill was requiring companies to have at least 5% disabled to work in companies was not complied. Therefore, PWD were left behind to enjoy the right to work and participate in the community's economic adherence.

Bullying: PWD students were discriminated and not accepted by non-SPED teachers. Teachers were observed of not accepting the good side of SPED students and were not given extra care for them. Employers reject PWD especially those with hearing impairment by not informing accurately about their salary. The non-PWD received higher wage than a PWD. Since the PWD could not defend much of himself the management and co-workers took advantage of them. Though HI communicated well through sign language, still he could not be understood because the other side didn't know how to understand sign language. Co-workers bullied the HI co-employee by making faces or tag names.

Adjustment to Environment: Persons with Autism had difficulty to change in the environment. They were characterized to be very structured.

Unavailability of School: Some schools did not offer courses to the PWD who will be enrolling in the collegiate level. Due to lack of facilities and trained SPED faculty for SPED students in college, this resulted SPED students to enroll the course they didn't prioritize.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the transition services of PWD in school are based on the Technology and Livelihood Education subjects and K-12 tracks. To achieve successful transition goal for PWD, teacher collaborates with the parents and vice versa. For employment, PWD can work variedly as persons with hearing impairment usually can work on manipulative jobs such as baker, bar tender, computer graphic artist, cook, delivery crew and product packager. Persons with visual impairment can hold a high ranking position in their workplaces. Meanwhile, persons with Autism and Down syndrome can be successful in their chosen work based on their talents and interests. Parents' assistance is more advisable. Parents attribute the employment of their children to their interest and the degree of disability. Youth with disabilities seek accommodation to help them overcome their challenges. Situational analysis is imperative in formulating and conducting any program or project.

IMPLICATIONS

Based on the barriers mentioned above, PWD faced their challenges and gave solutions to their

problems as mentioned in the interviews and FGDs with PWD, parents and teachers. To face challenges among PWD with various disabilities, one must learn to be humble despite the different difficulties he/she experienced with people around her. For her, doing what is right is the best thing to possess. It is also important to know how to deal with other people for PWD who work in an office. Decision making skills are developed through collaboration with other employees. Someone should be independent in his studies to achieve his good future. Another with physical disability due to poliomyelitis became confident through the help of her siblings at home. Socialization that started early during elementary days for a visually impaired help him to become competent as an individual. The challenge for a visually impaired to live and study in other country proved her that she conquered her difficulties and limitations. Following the instructions from teachers and coaches improved to develop skills needed to live normally in a mainstreamed society.

For employed PWD, a good attitude towards work and good relationship with co-workers must be possessed to survive and stay longer in their chosen field of work. Trainings, constant practice and collaboration with manager develop one to become an effective worker. To be assertiveness, PWD can approach confidently what he/she need in the workplace or outside while traveling. Other people will understand more what assistance they can offer.

Parents having children with disabilities need to be involved in different support groups. Organization for disabilities lessens the burden among parents who experienced difficulty in handling their children with disabilities. Parents with the same situation could share feelings and experiences to lighten their load. Family support within family members becomes stronger in caring and sharing for everyone's needs. Furthermore, community support enables among neighboring families ease one's family with a daughter with disability. They can be a protector in times of needs.

Teacher assists by being an interpreter for HI who applies for work. The teacher gives referral to agencies where PWD can get assistance for work and other livelihood purposes. Teacher also gives advices to prepare them in college education. Other teacher trains them to engage in business. Teacher suggests that HI should increase vocabulary and develop grammar syntax. It will be more advantageous in applying for a job in case there is no interpreter to assist him/her. Employer will understand more and communication will not be a barrier any more between them. Teacher's acceptance to PWD in the classroom must be imposed. They are the ones

who can help well while they are in school. Teacher in school has a great influence to the students to be engaged in business by selling products to parents with business establishments. The connection of teacher and business-oriented parents paved the way to develop socialization and to get interested in earning a living.

After secondary education, teacher searched for school that their students could enroll. They made sure of the availability of courses being offered for their PWD students. SPED teachers promoted a zero rejection in school. Nonetheless, these teachers preferred the PWD students to enroll in college where facilities and trained faculty members were present. To be guided constantly, the school administration advised their student to enroll in college preferably with SPED program to have a continuous SPED services and support. With the school full support to their PWD student in sports and academic activities, they became medalists in contests nationwide or worldwide.

Given that prevalent problems are still experienced by PWD in school and workplaces, the study recommends that the Department of Education, Commission on Higher Education, and Technical Education and Skills Development Authority to finalize their draft of transition program to be implemented in all public and private institution. Disseminate an order on the procedure of transition program in order to have a unified implementation. All PWD will benefit from all over the country and no one will be left behind especially in developing skills for employment purposes and sustaining adult life. Business sector must practice the law provided by the government for PWD. Encourage and welcome applicants to create more jobs for PWD. Orient regular employees to gain knowledge about different disabilities through seminars and meeting. PWD must develop and maintain self-advocacy and self-determination skills in secondary education to survive in the adult life. Talents and interests should be more enhanced through trainings and schooling. Finish education as much as possible with the abilities and capabilities possessed. Socialization with peers in school with non PWD starting from the basic education and collaboration with co-workers of adult PWD in their workplaces developed independence and self-confidence. To be employed among PWD develops the attitude of patience, diligence, assertiveness, collaborativeness and strong decision making. Parents must continue on collaborating with teachers, centers, and other institutions for the child's developing needs. It is important to know the disability, interest, ability, capability of the child and engage in organizations that will support both parent's and children's needs.

Encourage siblings to introduce their PWD children to their friends and other institution for work. Provide responsibilities at home like cooking, car washing, and other household chores. Introduce to the community for assistance and moral support. Regular and SPED teachers must accept students in the classroom whatever disability they do have and provide their needs. Encourage the regular students to collaborate with students with disabilities by providing classroom activities that will engage both by regular students and PWD. This will avoid first and foremost the barriers between them by learning each other's experiences. Assist as interpreter for HI in applying jobs. Look for linkages that will tie-up with school for livelihood programs. Train students to entrepreneurial activities in school. Introduce to barangay officials for safety and security around the school. Train students with Autism to be familiarized with places that could help them in the adjustment to environment. School Administration must provide accommodation and auxillary services for PWD like speech therapy so that child with special needs whose parents have low income can benefit. Prepare and provide concrete transition program to give direction for PWD at post-secondary education. Conduct seminars and symposia for non-SPED teachers to orient them in handling and accepting PWD students in their school. Set programs and activities involving parents for more collaboration. Future Researchers must conduct more researches on this study to update and improve the needs of PWD for their career path thereby preparing themselves in their adulthood.

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